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Research Article

EFFICACY OF KETAMINE/PROPOFOL VS LIGNOCAINE / PROPOFOL MIXTURES IN DECREASING PAIN ON INJECTION OF PROPOFOL 1% AT THE TIME OF INDUCTION

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Abstract:

Propofol is a commonly used inducer in everyday anesthetic practice, especially in the absence of thiopentone sodium. The disadvantage of this remedy is pain at the injection site, which is sometimes very severe. A higher concentration of propofol in the aqueous phase of the preparation causes greater pain during injection, while the addition of 1% lidocaine or 1% ketamine in a saline solution to propofol reduces pain. The low concentration of these agents and the observed rapid pain relief indicate that a mechanism other than the local anesthetic effect is also involved, and possibly a change in pH as well.

Aim: *We conducted a clinical trial to investigate the effects of changing the pH by adding lidocaine or ketamine in saline with propofol at the time of injection to see the patient's pain response.*

Methods: *The study was approved by our hospital management and written informed consent was obtained. This was a prospective, randomized, double-blind comparison of the lignocaine / propofol mixture with the ketamine / propofol mixture for pain following injection of propofol. A total of 80 adult patients (aged 18 to 65; ASA grade I or II) were recruited into the study. This study was held in the Anesthesia Unit II of Mayo Hospital Lahore for one-year duration from March 2019 to March 2020.*

18 parts of 1% propofol was mixed with 2 ml of 1% ketamine or 1% lidocaine. The pH of both solutions was measured.

Results and Conclusion: *The lowering of the pH due to the addition of these solutions to propofol is considered to be the cause of pain relief because if the same agents were administered before propofol without mixing them, the pain did not completely resolve. Thus, pH changes may modify propofol-induced pain on injection by a mechanism different from the effect of the local anesthetic on the vascular endothelium.*

Key words: *propofol, pH, injection pain, lidocaine 1%, ketamine 1%*

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INTRODUCTION:

The mechanism by which propofol causes pain when injected is still unknown. Several methods have been used to alleviate the pain caused by propofol upon injection. The use of lignocaine in the prevention of pain associated with injection of propofol is the most popular method used in clinical practice. The mechanism of this effect remains unclear. A local anesthetic effect of lignocaine or lowering the pH of the propofol lignocaine mixture as compared to propofol alone has been suggested. Eriksson *et al.* Suggested that changes in pH may modify pain caused by injection of propofol through a mechanism other than the effect of a local anesthetic on the vascular endothelium. They showed that lignocaine mixed with propofol lowers its pH, resulting in a lower concentration of propofol in the aqueous phase, and thus less pain. Ketamine has a local anesthetic effect when it is administered intravenously under local anesthesia. Pretreatment with ketamine has been shown to be effective in preventing pain from injecting propofol. The pH values of pharmaceutical ketamine solutions range from 3.5 to 5.5. We postulated that ketamine mixed with propofol could lower the pH of the mixed solution and reduce pain after injection of propofol in a mechanism similar to the addition of lignocaine. To determine if the pH change achieved by adding ketamine to propofol or lignocaine to propofol was more effective in relieving pain, we investigated the effectiveness of adding ketamine or lignocaine to propofol before injecting propofol. The change in pH due to the addition of ketamine or lignocaine to the propofol solution was measured.

METHODS:

The study was approved by our hospital management and written informed consent was obtained. This was a prospective, randomized, double-blind comparison of the lignocaine / propofol mixture with the ketamine / propofol mixture for pain following injection of propofol. A total of 80 adult patients (aged 18 to 65; ASA grade I or II) were recruited into the study. This study was held in the Anesthesia Unit II of Mayo Hospital Lahore for one-year duration from March 2019 to March 2020.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Patients taking regular painkillers or opioids
 2. Patients with acute or chronic pain syndromes
 3. Patients under the influence of sedatives
 4. Patients with communication problems.
- No premedication was given. After the patient arrived in the operating room, a 20G cannula was inserted into the vein on the back of the patient's hand. Intraoperative physiological monitoring included electrocardiography, non-invasive blood pressure measurement and pulse oximetry. Patients

were randomly assigned to one of the two groups by the sealed envelope method. Anesthesia was introduced and the data were collected by an anesthesiologist who was unaware of the purpose of the treatment. Patients in group K (ketamine) received a racemic mixture of ketamine 10 mg in 0.9% N / S 1.0 ml + 1% propofol 9 ml, followed by propofol infusion. Patients in group L (lignocaine) received 10 mg of lignocaine in 0.9% N / S 1.0 ml + 1% propofol 9 ml, followed by propofol infusion. Identically coded syringes were prepared by a nurse not involved in the study. The first 5 ml bolus was delivered within 5 seconds; 15 seconds later the patient was asked about the presence of pain after the injection. Pain at the time of injection was scored on a four-point scale of 8: 0 = no pain, 1 = mild pain (pain reported only in response to questions), 2 = moderate pain (pain reported to questions and accompanied by signs of behavior or pain reported spontaneously). no questions asked) and 3 = severe pain (strong vocal or reaction accompanied by a grimace, withdrawal of a hand or tears). The dose of ketamine used was based on the results of a previous study by Tan *et al.* Which assessed the analgesic effect of ketamine on pain following injection of propofol. Propofol injection was continued until complete anesthesia was induced. Anesthesia was maintained with 1.0% isoflurane and 60% nitrous oxide in oxygen 40%. Awakening reactions defined as dreams, hallucinations and deliriums were recorded by direct questioning after the patient recovered from anesthesia. We used propofol (1%) and ketamine and lignocaine. The pH of 1% propofol, ketamine, lignocaine, a mixture of propofol and ketamine and a mixture of propofol and lignocaine were measured with a pH meter.

RESULTS:

Both groups were comparable in terms of age, sex, weight and height (Table 1). The overall incidence of post-injection pain was significantly lower in the L group (28, 30%) compared to the K group (48, 51%), $P = 0.005$. Post-injection pain severity, rated as none, mild, moderate or severe, showed a statistically significant benefit for group L versus group K ($P = 0.015$) (Table 2). There were no significant differences in mean blood pressure and heart rate between the groups. Table 1: Data are presented as number of patients or as mean $\pm$ SD. There was no statistically significant difference between the two groups. The dose of ketamine used did not raise blood pressure or prevent the propofol-induced reduction in blood pressure that occurs prior to intubation. There were no rising reactions. The pH of 1% of propofol was 7.86 and the pH of ketamine was 4.08. The pH of a mixture of 1% propofol 9 ml with 10 mg ketamine in 1.0 ml N / S is 5.84. The pH of 1% lignocaine was 6.75

and the pH of 1% propofol 9 ml with 10 mg

lignocaine in N / S 1.0 ml was 6.57.

Table 1: Data are presented as either number of patients or as mean $\pm$ SD. There was no statistically significant difference between the two groups.

Group	Group K	Group L
N	40	40
Age (y)	49 $\pm$ 15	45 $\pm$ 16
Weight (kg)	63 $\pm$ 12	66 $\pm$ 12
Height (cm)	161 $\pm$ 9	164 $\pm$ 10
Gender (M/F)	15/25	13/27

Table 2: The incidence and severity of pain was significantly different between the groups ($P < 0.05$).

Group	Group K	Group L
No pain	46 (49%)	66 (70%)
Mild	26 (28%)	18 (19%)
Moderate	14 (15%)	8 (9%)
Severe	8 (8%)	2 (2%)

DISCUSSION:

The overall incidence of post-injection pain was significantly lower in the L group (28 [30%] compared to the K group (48 [51%], $P = 0.005$). This study showed that a mixture of propofol and lignocaine (10 mg lignocaine in 10 ml propofol) is more effective than a mixture of propofol ketamine (10 mg ketamine in 10 ml propofol). It may be that the pH is lowered more compared to the propofol-ketamine mixture. The mechanism of pain following injection of propofol remains unclear. A number of mechanisms have been proposed. Scott et al. Suggested that the pain is likely to result from direct irritation or indirect through the kinin cascade. It has been suggested that the concentration of propofol in the aqueous phase may be an important variable for pain associated with injection of propofol. reduced. More recently, Eriksson et al. Discovered that the pH of propofol decreased in a dose-dependent manner when mixed with 1% lignocaine. The concentration of propofol in the aqueous phase was lower when propofol was mixed with 1% lignocaine or ketamine. The addition of lignocaine to propofol caused the migration of propofol from the aqueous phase of the propofol emulsion to the lipid phase. The increased proportion of propofol in the lipid phase resulted in less pain upon injection. The mechanism of ketamine's analgesic effects is the same. There was an inverse relationship between the pH and the amount of ketamine added, as was the case with mixtures of propofol lignocaine which lowers the pH, reduces pain after injection of propofol. Several studies have shown ketamine use to be effective. Contrary to our study, Koo et al. Reported that a mixture of propofol and ketamine

(ketamine 100 μ g / kg) did not reduce pain after injection of propofol compared to pretreatment with saline. However, the volume ratio of the mixture was not described in this study. Nevertheless, in this study, we did not find any adverse effects after the use of propofol ketamine mixtures, and no color change or a non-miscible surface layer was found upon inspection. Several methods have been tried to reduce the incidence of pain after injection of propofol with varying effect, e.g. using solutions at different temperatures, dilution of propofol, different injection sites and different methods of combining ephedrine, ondansetron, metoclopramide, opioids, thiopentone. The most frequently cited side effect associated with ketamine is sudden delirium or hallucinations. This is more common when ketamine is used as the sole sedative, and generally at higher doses than those used in this study. In the present study, no patient reported an emergency reaction. Combining ketamine with propofol can eliminate this effect of ketamine.

CONCLUSION:

The mixture of propofol and lignocaine was found to be more effective in reducing the incidence of pain after injection of propofol than the mixture of ketamine and propofol. Our results confirm pH changes as the more important cause of pain reduction after injection of propofol when ketamine or lignocaine is added to propofol.

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